

PENGWIN 2026: Peripelvic Fracture Segmentation and Reduction Planning Challenge: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

PENGWIN 2026: Peripelvic Fracture Segmentation and Reduction Planning Challenge

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

PENGWIN 2026

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Peripelvic fractures are typically caused by high-energy trauma and are among the most severe injuries, with disability rates exceeding 50% and mortality rates over 13%, making them the deadliest among all complex fractures. The intricate anatomy of the pelvis and the surrounding soft tissues render surgical interventions particularly challenging. In recent years, there has been a shift from open reduction to image-guided manual or robot-assisted fracture reduction surgeries, which have demonstrated improved surgical outcomes. Consequently, an intelligent surgical planning pipeline is crucial. By integrating automated segmentation with reduction planning, the comprehensive workflow significantly enhances the efficiency, objectivity, and precision of surgical decision-making compared to traditional labor-intensive and expertise-demanding manual approaches.

Due to the diverse shapes and positions of bone fragments and the complex fracture surfaces resulting from bone collisions, segmenting peripelvic fracture fragments is technically challenging. Furthermore, determining the optimal geometric restoration of these multiple spatially separated fragments represents a high-dimensional, non-convex matching problem, often serving as a major bottleneck in surgical planning. Although deep learning has driven significant progress in general segmentation and reconstruction tasks within computer vision, applying these techniques directly to surgical workflows is still fraught with unique challenges. This is primarily due to the lack of algorithms specifically tailored for these complex orthopedic tasks and the scarcity of extensive image datasets with comprehensive annotations and ground-truth reduction poses.

In 2026, the PENGWIN Challenge will consist of three tasks aimed at evaluating and advancing state-of-the-art techniques: developing fully automated segmentation methods (Task 1), interactive segmentation methods (Task 2), and fracture reduction planning methods (Task 3) for 3D CT of peripelvic fractures. Our dataset has been

significantly expanded to include CT scans from 500 clinical patients (incorporating 350 new cases) scheduled for peripelvic reduction surgery, collected from seven institutions using various scanning devices, representing a wide range of patient populations and fracture types. To support the training of data-driven reduction models (Task 3), we additionally provide 16,000 simulated fracture cases generated from 400 healthy peripelvic CTs using advanced fracture simulation algorithms. To ensure accurate performance evaluation, multiple orthopedic medical experts conducted comprehensive annotations and cross-checks on the training, validation, and testing datasets. The primary objective of the PENGWIN Challenge is to foster innovative research in intelligent surgical planning while establishing foundational resources for future peripelvic-related studies and interdisciplinary collaborations.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Peripelvic fracture, Computer-assisted orthopedic surgery, Image Segmentation, Reduction Planning, CT, PENGWIN, Automation, Interaction

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

Building on the robust foundation established by the PENGWIN 2024 Challenge, PENGWIN 2026 significantly expands the clinical scale and introduces a comprehensive 3D workflow including interactive segmentation and fracture reduction planning. The main innovations include the following aspects:

(1) Large-Scale, Expert-Annotated Hybrid Dataset with Increased Diversity: The clinical dataset is expanded to 500 diverse 3D pelvic CT scans (up from 150 in 2024), covering a wider spectrum of fracture patterns including complex pelvic ring disruptions, acetabular fractures, and proximal femoral fractures. For the first time, we provide high-precision fracture reduction planning labels, establishing a unique benchmark for 3D restoration. To further enhance the richness and diversity of the reduction planning dataset, we provide 16,000 high-fidelity simulated cases as additional resources, offering the "pre-injury" ground truth typically missing in real-world scans.

(2) Clinically Aligned Segmentation Methods: Moving away from simulated X-rays, the challenge now focuses on fully automated (Task 1) and interactive (Task 2) 3D CT segmentation. This setup promotes innovation in both autonomous algorithms for routine cases and user-assisted techniques for high-stakes, complex fractures where expert-in-the-loop is clinically essential.

(3) Evolution from Perception to Planning A pivotal milestone of this year's challenge is the introduction of Task 3 (Fracture Reduction Planning). This addition creates a task-triad that shifts the focus from static anatomical "perception" (segmentation) to therapeutic "action" (restoration). This evolution reflects the actual requirements of modern digital orthopedics by transitioning from merely "seeing" the fracture to "solving" the mechanical restoration.

(4) Driving Clinical Impact and Research Progress: Directly supporting critical applications such as fracture classification, pre-operative planning, and robotic-assisted reduction, the challenge improves patient care and drives the development of advanced surgical intelligence. It also establishes foundational resources for future research and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Peripelvic fracture segmentation can be directly supports fracture diagnosis and surgical navigation, including fracture classification and 3D-3D registration of CT-CBCT, and 3D-2D registration of CT-X-ray. Building on this, fracture reduction planning provides the essential algorithmic foundation for screw fixation planning and robotic-assisted reduction.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

The anticipated number of participants for our challenge is approximately 300, based on the interest demonstrated in PENGWIN 2024 and similar challenges within the medical imaging community. The PENGWIN challenge at MICCAI 2024 attracted 235 registered participants, 197 submissions, and 3,000 dataset downloads, reflecting strong community interest in the peripelvic fracture segmentation task. Other similar challenges have also been highly popular. For example, the RibFrac challenge at MICCAI 2020 attracted 356 registered participants, 243 submissions, and 25,000 dataset downloads, further highlighting the community's engagement with fracture-related tasks. In the PENGWIN challenge at MICCAI 2026, we significantly expand the scope by offering three tasks: fully automated segmentation, interactive segmentation, and a novel fracture reduction planning task. This comprehensive design will appeal to a broader range of researchers, encompassing expertise in automation, interactive techniques, and geometric restoration for surgical planning. Additionally, we plan to send email notifications to potential participants to inform them about this year's challenge.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to coordinate 3 specific publication plans after the challenge.

Plan 1: After the challenge concludes, the organizers will publish a journal paper that comprehensively covers all aspects of the competition. This paper will provide an in-depth description of the algorithms developed by the participants, along with a thorough analysis of their performance and unique features.

Plan 2: We will consolidate the results of the interactive segmentation task from this challenge with those from other interactive challenges organized by us and publish a journal paper that offers a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art techniques in interactive segmentation.

Plan 3: We will publish a specific study focused on the peripelvic fracture reduction planning task. This paper will evaluate the generalization capability of the submitted algorithms by comparing their performance on the large-scale Simulated Test Set versus the Clinical Test Set, establishing the first benchmark for geometric fracture restoration.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We will use grand-challenge.org as the online platform.

TASK 1: PENGWIN-Auto: Automatic Peripelvic Fracture Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Peripelvic fractures, primarily caused by high-energy trauma, are among the most severe injuries, with a disability rate exceeding 50% and a mortality rate over 13%. These injuries are the deadliest among complex fractures, presenting significant challenges for surgical intervention due to the intricate anatomy of the pelvis and surrounding soft tissues. Accurate segmentation of peripelvic injuries in 3D CT scans is essential for effective trauma diagnosis and image-guided surgical planning [1]. High-quality segmentation directly influences critical tasks such as fracture classification, preoperative reduction planning, and screw fixation, ultimately improving surgical outcomes and patient care [2,3].

Despite its importance, peripelvic fracture segmentation remains a difficult task due to the variability in the size, shape, and number of fracture fragments, along with the irregular and complex surfaces created by bone collisions. These challenges are exacerbated by a lack of annotated datasets, which limits the development and application of advanced data-driven segmentation methods. Inaccurate segmentation can lead to misdiagnoses, flawed surgical plans, and increased complications, underscoring the need for reliable, automated solutions.

Building on previous efforts, PENGWIN 2026 significantly expands its dataset to 500 clinical cases sourced from multiple institutions and imaging systems, offering enhanced diversity and robustness [4]. This extensive dataset encompasses a wide spectrum of injury patterns, including joint dislocations, various pelvic fractures, acetabular fractures, and proximal femoral fractures. Participants are invited to develop and containerize various algorithms using training data, evaluate and refine them using unseen validation data until July 2026, and assess the performance of their final submitted algorithm using hidden test data. Evaluation metrics such as Intersection over Union (IoU), Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95), and Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC) will be used to measure segmentation accuracy, alongside Recognition Quality (RQ) for instance-level evaluation. The challenge aims to identify state-of-the-art automated segmentation algorithms that streamline clinical workflows, improve precision, and enhance patient outcomes.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Computed tomography, Peripelvic fractures, Automatic segmentation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yanzhen Liu, Beihang University
 Yudi Sang, Rossum Robot
 Sutuke Yibulayimu, Beihang University
 Yu Wang, Beihang University
 Gang Zhu, Rossum Robot
 Benjamin D. Killeen, Johns Hopkins University
 Mingxu Liu, Johns Hopkins University
 Ping-Cheng Ku, Johns Hopkins University
 Ronald Man Yeung Wong, CUHK Medical Centre
 Elvis Chun Sing Chui, CUHK Medical Centre
 Mehran Armand, Johns Hopkins University
 Mathias Unberath, Johns Hopkins University
 Xinbao Wu, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital
 Chunpeng Zhao, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital
 Zdravko Marinov, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
 Rainer Stiefelhagen, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
 Dan Ruan, University of California, Los Angeles
 S. Kevin Zhou, University of Science and Technology of China

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yanzhen Liu
 Beihang University
 yanzhenliu@buaa.edu.cn

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Clinicians from Beijing Jishuitan Hospital and CUHK Medical Centre are integral to the team. Their roles include: (1) guiding data acquisition protocols to ensure clinical relevance; (2) establishing a rigorous annotation protocol for the 500 cases based on real-world clinical scenarios; and (3) verifying the clinical validity of segmentation results to ensure they meet the accuracy requirements for surgical application.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

A challenge website is planned to be launched upon acceptance of the challenge proposal.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic. No user interaction is allowed at any step

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may supplement the training dataset with additional data from public datasets or their own institutions. However, if they choose to do so, they must specify and discuss the potential differences in results compared to using only the PENGWIN 2026 dataset. Any external data used must be publicly available.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 teams will receive cash awards (\$1000, \$500, and \$200, funded by Rossum Robot) and certificates. They will be invited to co-author the challenge summary paper.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be shown publicly on the challenge leaderboard, which will be updated daily during the open validation round and announced on the final round phases of the closed test round of the task.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The challenge organizers will publish at least one challenge journal paper and potentially more. Up to two team members in each of the top-performing teams qualify as authors for joint publication. Participants are allowed to publish their results separately after the challenge. The publication embargo period will be 12 months after the announcement of the challenge results.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission on Grand Challenge.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants can have multiple submissions on the validation data during the validation phase. For the testing phase, only the last run of the submitted Docker container is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge websites open: 04/01/2026

Training data release: 04/05/2026

Validation data release and results submission: 05/15/2026

Final Submission deadline: 07/31/2026

Result release: 08/31/2026

Presentation at conference: 10/2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The retrospective data collection, share, and usage strictly conformed to ethical standards and was approved by the ethical committee of Beijing Jishuitan Hospital (Approval number 202009-04).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The metric calculation code will be released along with the validation data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The top 3 performing methods are required to share their code on a public repository. Other teams are also encouraged to share their code. Links to the available source code will be referenced on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is sponsored by Rossum Robot. Only the organizers (Rossum Robot, IMR Lab of Beihang University, BIGSS Lab and ARCADE Lab of Johns Hopkins University and cv:hci Lab of Karlsruhe Institute of Technology) will have access to the test case labels during the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Surgery, Intervention planning, CAD, Diagnosis, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients with peripelvic trauma undergoing CT scans.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The subject of peripelvic trauma who planned to undergo fracture reduction surgery after pre-operative CT scanning.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed tomography (CT)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Along with the images, ground-truth segmentation labels of the sacrum, left hipbone, right hipbone, left femur, right femur, and bone fragments will be provided.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No further patient information will be provided.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Peripelvic region shown in CT data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

All bone fragments within the peripelvic region.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision, Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT scans were acquired using a diverse array of devices from multiple manufacturers, including TOSHIBA (Aquilion PRIME, Aquilion ONE), UNITED IMAGING (uCT 550), PHILIPS (Brilliance 64), SIEMENS (Sensation 64, SOMATOM Force), and GE (Optima CT660).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Clinically-used routine CT protocols have been used in each CT scanner. During the acquisition process, all patients were positioned in supine pose. The average voxel spacing is $0.81 \times 0.81 \times 0.93 \text{ mm}^3$. The typical image dimensions average at $483 \times 385 \times 320$.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The CT data for this challenge were acquired from a multi-center consortium comprising seven clinical institutions to ensure data diversity and robustness. These centers include Beijing Jishuitan Hospital, Foshan Hospital of Traditional Chinese Medicine, The First Hospital of Jilin University, The Second Hospital of Jilin University, Nanfang Hospital (Southern Medical University), Tongji Hospital, and CUHK Medical Centre.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

CT acquisition was performed by professional radiologists.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a CT scan of a patient with peripelvic trauma, and both have an expert-validated annotation provided for each bone fragment.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The 500 cases are split into 350 for training, 50 for validation, and 100 for testing.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The test cases are sufficiently broad to cover each CT scanner type and each fracture type. Considering the large image size for the CT scans, the number of test cases was set to 100 to limit the total runtime and computational cost for performing the evaluation.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

To ensure a balanced and representative evaluation, we employed stratified random sampling based on peripelvic injury patterns. This ensures that the training, validation, and test sets share the same distribution of fracture types.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

For this challenge, the dataset consists of 500 cases in total. Of these, 150 cases are carried over from PENGWIN2024, while the remaining 350 cases are new, unseen, and unpublished data. These new cases have been incorporated into the dataset for this challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The dataset is processed by three experienced annotators and two senior experts. The data annotation was structured into a four-step workflow:

- (1) Initial automatic segmentation: We employ a pre-trained segmentation network based on the nnUnet framework to produce preliminary segmentations for the sacrum, hipbones, and femurs [5]. This network was trained on roughly 1,000 peripelvic CT images, with the majority of them not presenting any fractures [6].
- (2) Manual refinement of anatomical labels: The initial anatomical labels undergo a meticulous refinement process by annotators using the 3D Slicer platform.
- (3) Identification of fractured fragments: Leveraging the refined anatomical labels, the annotators identify and label fractured bone fragments. This operation is also carried out on the 3D Slicer platform.
- (4) Expert validation: As a final checkpoint, two senior experts rigorously.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotators are asked to annotate the five anatomical labels (sacrum, left hipbone, right hipbone, left femur, and right femur) and the bone fragment within each bone, using the 3D Slicer platform. When a bone is considered intact without presenting any fracture, the only fragment is its anatomical mask itself. Fragments with volume less than 500 mm^3 are omitted.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The dataset is processed by three experienced annotators and two senior experts. All of them has more than five year experience on pelvis-related study or surgery.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The CT scans and the corresponding labels are manually cropped to the pelvis region when the original field of view is too large (greater than 0.5 meter on z-axis).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The source of error may come from annotations of the half-cracked and connected patterns in some (about 10%) fracture cases, where determining the fracture line involves higher inter-observer variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Another source of error comes from the comminuted fracture regions with small bone shards, where the annotators have to determine whether it belongs to a fragment label.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

(1) Intersection over Union (IoU)

(2) Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD)

(3) 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95)

(4) Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC)**(5) Recognition Quality (RQ)**

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

These metrics were chosen for their ability to comprehensively evaluate anatomical and fracture segmentation. The Intersection over Union (IoU) quantifies the overlap between predicted and ground-truth regions, while the Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD) and the 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95) capture boundary discrepancies and mitigate outlier effects. Additionally, the Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC) provides a localized assessment of segmentation accuracy, offering finer-grained evaluation in regions of interest. Finally, Recognition Quality (RQ) is employed to assess instance-level performance, specifically quantifying the algorithm's ability to correctly identify and separate individual bone fragments. Together, these metrics ensure both accurate regional segmentation and precise anatomical delineation.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

In this multi-label segmentation task, the ranking process is designed to comprehensively evaluate anatomical segmentation and fracture segmentation. By evaluating each case individually and averaging the results, we ensure that all cases, regardless of their inherent difficulty, contribute equally to the final ranking determination.

(1) Metric calculation: On an individual case level, compute IoU, HD95, and ASSD for anatomical segmentation, and IoU, HD95, ASSD, LDSC, and RQ for fracture segmentation. For fragment instance segmentation, match each ground truth instance with the predicted instance that has the highest IoU.

(2) Metric Ranking: Rank the average results for each metric separately for each submission.

(3) Subtask Ranking: Determine separate rankings for anatomical segmentation and fracture segmentation by averaging the corresponding metric ranks for each submission.

(4) Final Ranking: Compute the final rank for each submission by averaging its ranks across all metrics.

(5) Tie-Breaking: Use the total execution time of the submissions to break any ties in the final ranking.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, the metric will be assigned its worst possible value. Specifically, the Intersection over Union (IoU) will be set to 0, indicating no overlap between the predicted and true labels. For the Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), the metric will be set to the radius of the fragment's minimum enclosing sphere, and the 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95) will be set to the diameter of the fragment's minimum enclosing sphere. Similarly, the Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC) will be set to 0, reflecting complete segmentation failure in the local region of interest. Finally, the Recognition Quality (RQ) will be set to 0, signifying a complete failure to identify any valid bone fragment instances.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

(1) We adopt the rank-then-aggregate method to ensure robustness against varying user behaviors. Ranking metrics separately prevents unbounded metrics (like HD95) from dominating bounded metrics (like IoU).

(2) By computing separate subtask rankings, we ensure the final winner excels in both anatomical reconstruction and fracture fragment identification.

(3) Averaging ranks across all cases ensures that difficult cases do not disproportionately skew the final result.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will report the Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and 95% Confidence Intervals (CI) for all metrics.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Precision of the performance estimates for each algorithm will be assessed using 95% confidence intervals (CI) calculated via percentile bootstrap (1,000 resamples). This will be applied to all primary metrics, including IoU, ASSD, HD95, LDSC, and RQ, to quantify the statistical reliability of each team's reported performance across the clinical test set.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Box plots will be used to visualize the distribution of metrics across test cases. We will report the Standard Deviation (SD) and identify outliers (cases beyond 1.5x IQR) to analyze failure modes.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking robustness will be evaluated via bootstrap analysis with 1,000 resamples of the clinical test set. The stability of the outcome will be quantified using the Kendall rank correlation coefficient (τ) and its 95% confidence interval (CI), ensuring that the final leaderboard is statistically reliable and resistant to test-set bias.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

A Paired t-test (or Wilcoxon signed-rank test if data is not normally distributed) will be used to compare the top-performing methods. Significance level is set at $p < 0.05$.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing data is handled via worst-case penalization. Specifically, IoU, LDSC, and RQ are set to 0, while ASSD and HD95 are assigned the radius and diameter of the fragment's minimum enclosing sphere, respectively.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python (SciPy, NumPy, Matplotlib, etc.)

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,

- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

A dockerized baseline model will be provided for benchmarking purposes. Future analyses will include a comprehensive report on inter-algorithm variability to evaluate comparative performance stability. Furthermore, we will stratify performance analysis by "Fracture Complexity" (according to AO/OTA classification) to identify potential biases and ensure clinical generalizability.

Reference:

- [1] Ge, Yufeng, et al. "Robot-assisted autonomous reduction of a displaced pelvic fracture: a case report and brief literature review." *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 11.6 (2022): 1598.
- [2] Moolenaar, Jet Zoë, Nazli Tümer, and Sara Checa. "Computer-assisted preoperative planning of bone fracture fixation surgery: A state-of-the-art review." *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* 10 (2022): 1037048.
- [3] Liu, Yanzhen, et al. "Pelvic Fracture Segmentation Using a Multi-scale Distance-Weighted Neural Network." *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023.
- [4] Sang, Yudi, et al. "Benchmark of Segmentation Techniques for Pelvic Fracture in CT and X-ray: Summary of the PENGWIN 2024 Challenge." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.02382* (2025).
- [5] Isensee, Fabian, et al. "nnU-Net: a self-configuring method for deep learning-based biomedical image segmentation." *Nature methods* 18.2 (2021): 203-211.
- [6] Liu, Pengbo, et al. "Deep learning to segment pelvic bones: large-scale CT datasets and baseline models." *International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery* 16 (2021): 749-756.

TASK 2: PENGWIN-Interact: Interactive Peripelvic Fracture Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Peripelvic fractures, often resulting from high-energy trauma, are among the most critical injuries, with disability rates exceeding 50% and mortality rates above 13%. Precise segmentation of peripelvic injuries in 3D CT scans is essential for accurate diagnosis, effective surgical planning, and intraoperative navigation [1]. Unlike fully automated approaches, interactive segmentation integrates user inputs, such as clicks or bounding boxes, to address complexities like varying fragment counts and challenging annotations [2].

The PENGWIN 2026 initiative expands its focus to include interactive segmentation, enabling clinicians to guide model predictions with intuitive inputs. This new task employs a diverse dataset of 300 well-annotated cases from multiple institutions and imaging systems, encompassing a wide spectrum of injury patterns, including joint dislocations, various pelvic fractures, acetabular fractures, and proximal femoral fractures [3]. Standardized pre-simulated click data, generated programmatically, will be made available to all participants as additional data to the CT images, ensuring consistent evaluation and facilitating external model fine-tuning. Participants will develop interactive algorithms using the provided training data, validate their solutions on unseen cases by July 2026, and submit containerized models for final evaluation on a hidden test set.

Evaluation criteria will include segmentation accuracy metrics such as the Intersection over Union (IoU), Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), and 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95). Additionally, the Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC) is introduced to provide a localized assessment of segmentation accuracy, alongside Recognition Quality (RQ) for instance-level evaluation. Interaction-specific metrics will also measure user-model collaboration, emphasizing the utilization of interactions required to achieve optimal segmentation quality. This challenge aims to drive advancements in interactive peripelvic fracture segmentation, promoting the development of clinically viable solutions. To further foster innovation, the initiative will feature a centralized leaderboard in partnership with other interactive segmentation challenges, encouraging collaboration and progress in this growing field.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Computed tomography, Peripelvic fractures, Interactive segmentation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Zdravko Marinov, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
 Yanzhen Liu, Beihang University
 Rainer Stiefelhagen, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
 Yudi Sang, Rossum Robot
 Sutuke Yibulayimu, Beihang University
 Jingjiang Qin, Beihang University
 Yu Wang, Beihang University
 Gang Zhu, Rossum Robot
 Xinbao Wu, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital
 Chunpeng Zhao, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital
 Ronald Man Yeung Wong, CUHK Medical Centre
 Elvis Chun Sing Chui, CUHK Medical Centre
 Mehran Armand, Johns Hopkins University
 Dan Ruan, University of California, Los Angeles
 S. Kevin Zhou, University of Science and Technology of China

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Zdravko Marinov
 Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
 zdravko.marinov@kit.edu

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Clinicians from Beijing Jishuitan Hospital and CUHK Medical Centre are integral to the team. Their roles include: (1) guiding data acquisition protocols to ensure clinical relevance; (2) establishing a rigorous annotation protocol for the 500 cases based on real-world clinical scenarios; and (3) verifying the clinical validity of segmentation results to ensure they meet the accuracy requirements for surgical application.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

A challenge website is planned to be launched upon acceptance of the challenge proposal.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed during the training phase for data curation, cleaning, and quality control. However, no manual user interaction is allowed during the inference phase on the hidden test set. The algorithms must function fully automatically by processing the input images and the standardized pre-simulated interaction points (e.g., clicks) provided by the organizers to generate the segmentation results.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may supplement the training dataset with additional data from public datasets or their own institutions. However, if they choose to do so, they must specify and discuss the potential differences in results compared to using only the PENGWIN 2026 dataset. Any external data used must be publicly available.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 teams will receive cash awards (\$1000, \$500, and \$200, funded by Rossum Robot) and certificates. They will be invited to co-author the challenge summary paper.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be shown publicly on the challenge leaderboard, which will be updated daily during the open validation round and announced on the final round phases of the closed test round of the task.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The challenge organizers will publish at least one challenge journal paper and potentially more. Up to two team members in each of the top-performing teams qualify as authors for joint publication. Participants are allowed to publish their results separately after the challenge. The publication embargo period will be 12 months after the announcement of the challenge results.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission on Grand Challenge.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants can have multiple submissions on the validation data during the validation phase. For the testing phase, only the last run of the submitted Docker container is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge websites open: 04/01/2026

Training data release: 04/05/2026

Validation data release and results submission: 05/15/2026

Final Submission deadline: 07/31/2026

Result release: 08/31/2026

Presentation at conference: 10/2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The retrospective data collection, share, and usage strictly conformed to ethical standards and was approved by the ethical committee of Beijing Jishuitan Hospital (Approval number 202009-04).

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The metric calculation code will be released along with the validation data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The top 3 performing methods are required to share their code on a public repository. Other teams are also encouraged to share their code. Links to the available source code will be referenced on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is sponsored by Rossum Robot. Only the organizers (Rossum Robot, IMR Lab of Beihang University, BIGSS Lab and ARCADE Lab of Johns Hopkins University and cv:hci Lab of Karlsruhe Institute of Technology) will have access to the test case labels during the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Surgery, Intervention planning, CAD, Diagnosis, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients with peripelvic trauma undergoing CT scans.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The subject of peripelvic trauma who planned to undergo fracture reduction surgery after pre-operative CT scanning.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed tomography (CT)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Along with the images, ground-truth segmentation labels of the sacrum, left hipbone, right hipbone, left femur, right femur, and bone fragments will be provided. Additionally, four sets of click annotations for all fragments within each image will be provided as JSON files (containing point coordinates and foreground/background labels), derived from four distinct click simulation strategies. These JSON annotations will also indicate the number of fragments present in each image and facilitate the development of foundation models.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No further patient information will be provided.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Peripelvic region shown in CT data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

All bone fragments within the peripelvic region.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that

assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision, Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT scans were acquired using a diverse array of devices from multiple manufacturers, including TOSHIBA (Aquilion PRIME, Aquilion ONE), UNITED IMAGING (uCT 550), PHILIPS (Brilliance 64), SIEMENS (Sensation 64, SOMATOM Force), and GE (Optima CT660).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Clinically-used routine CT protocols have been used in each CT scanner. During the acquisition process, all patients were positioned in supine pose. The average voxel spacing is $0.81 \times 0.81 \times 0.93 \text{ mm}^3$. The typical image dimensions average at $483 \times 385 \times 320$.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The CT data for this challenge were acquired from a multi-center consortium comprising seven clinical institutions to ensure data diversity and robustness. These centers include Beijing Jishuitan Hospital, Foshan Hospital of Traditional Chinese Medicine, The First Hospital of Jilin University, The Second Hospital of Jilin University, Nanfang Hospital (Southern Medical University), Tongji Hospital, and CUHK Medical Centre.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

CT acquisition was performed by professional radiologists.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).

- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a CT scan of a patient with peripelvic trauma, with expert-validated annotations and a set of pre-simulated user clicks provided for each bone fragment present in the CT scan.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The 500 patients are split into 350 for training, 50 for validation, and 100 for testing. For each patient's data, four sets of clicks are generated, resulting in 1400, 200, and 400 for training, validation, and testing, respectively.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The test cases are sufficiently broad to cover each CT scanner type and each fracture type. Considering the large image size for the CT scans, the number of test cases was set to 100 to limit the total runtime and computational cost for performing the evaluation.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

To ensure a balanced and representative evaluation, we employed stratified random sampling based on peripelvic injury patterns. This ensures that the training, validation, and test sets share the same distribution of fracture types.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

For this challenge, the dataset consists of 500 cases in total. Of these, 150 cases are carried over from PENGWIN2024, while the remaining 350 cases are new, unseen, and unpublished data. These new cases have been incorporated into the dataset for this challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

In addition to the annotations provided in Task 1, click simulations will be generated for each peripelvic CT image using four distinct approaches, derived from its ground-truth labels:

- (1) clicking at the center of mass of each fragment [4].
- (2) uniformly sampling clicks within each fragment [5].
- (3) placing clicks near the boundary of each fragment as internal margin clicks [6].
- (4) sampling clicks within each fragment according to the Euclidean distance transform [7].

To prevent the task from being simplistic and to mimic realistic user behavior, the simulation algorithm will introduce spatial jitter to simulate human clicking errors. For each CT image, these simulations will generate four

different click-annotation styles, resulting in four distinct cases.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

In addition to the annotations provided in Task 1, each image will be accompanied by click data for each fragment present, with coordinates provided in the image's resolution. To ensure a fair and consistent comparison across interactive approaches, all participants will receive the same four sets of pre-simulated clicks for each training image. Furthermore, we will make the code used to generate clicks for all four strategies available to participants, enabling them to replicate the click simulations on external training data and fine-tune their models accordingly.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The dataset is processed by three experienced annotators and two senior experts. All of them has more than five year experience on pelvis-related study or surgery. Simulated clicks will be cross-checked by senior experts after generation.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The CT scans and the corresponding labels are manually cropped to the pelvis region when the original field of view is too large (greater than 0.5 meter on z-axis).

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The source of error may come from annotations of the half-cracked and connected patterns in some (about 10%) fracture cases, where determining the fracture line involves higher inter-observer variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Another source of error comes from the comminuted fracture regions with small bone shards, where the annotators have to determine whether it belongs to a fragment label.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if

any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- (1) Intersection over Union (IoU)
- (2) Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD)
- (3) 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95)
- (4) Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC)
- (5) Recognition Quality (RQ)

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

These metrics were chosen for their ability to comprehensively evaluate anatomical and fracture segmentation. The Intersection over Union (IoU) quantifies the overlap between predicted and ground-truth regions, while the Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD) and the 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95) capture boundary discrepancies and mitigate outlier effects. Additionally, the Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC) provides a localized assessment of segmentation accuracy, offering finer-grained evaluation in regions of interest. Finally, Recognition Quality (RQ) is employed to assess instance-level performance, specifically quantifying the algorithm's ability to correctly identify and separate individual bone fragments. Together, these metrics ensure both accurate regional segmentation and precise anatomical delineation.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

We will adopt the widely recognized rank-then-aggregate method as our ranking approach. The metric calculation will be performed as follows:

- (1) Compute the original metrics (IoU, HD95, ASSD, LDSC, RQ) for each image using the four click simulation strategies, resulting in 20 metrics (4 strategies × 5 metrics).
- (2) Rank each team for each image based on the 20 individual metrics.
- (3) Aggregate the rankings for each metric across the four simulation schemes (e.g., $\text{IoU_rank_center} + \text{IoU_rank_uniform} + \text{IoU_rank_internal} + \text{IoU_rank_distance}$) to produce five independent rankings for the metrics (IoU, ASSD, HD95, LDSC, RQ).
- (4) Final Ranking: Determine the final rank for each submission by averaging all five ranks.
- (5) Tie-Breaking: Use the total execution time of the submissions to break any ties in the final ranking.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, the metric will be assigned its worst possible value. Specifically, the Intersection over Union (IoU) will be set to 0, indicating no overlap between the predicted and true labels. For the Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), the metric will be set to the radius of the fragment's minimum enclosing sphere, and the 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD95) will be set to the diameter of the fragment's minimum enclosing sphere. Similarly, the Local Dice Similarity Coefficient (LDSC) will be set to 0, reflecting complete segmentation failure in the local region of interest. Finally, the Recognition Quality (RQ) will be set to 0, signifying a complete failure to identify any valid bone fragment instances.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

- (1) We adopt the rank-then-aggregate method to ensure robustness against varying user behaviors. Ranking metrics separately prevents unbounded metrics (like HD95) from dominating bounded metrics (like IoU).
- (2) By aggregating results across four distinct simulation strategies, we reward algorithms that perform consistently regardless of how a user places clicks.
- (3) Averaging ranks across all cases ensures that difficult cases do not disproportionately skew the final result.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will report the Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and 95% Confidence Intervals (CI) for all metrics.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Precision of the performance estimates for each algorithm will be assessed using 95% confidence intervals (CI) calculated via percentile bootstrap (1,000 resamples). This will be applied to all primary metrics, including IoU, ASSD, HD95, LDSC, and RQ, to quantify the statistical reliability of each team's reported performance across the clinical test set.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Box plots will be used to visualize the distribution of metrics across test cases. We will report the Standard Deviation (SD) and identify outliers (cases beyond 1.5x IQR) to analyze failure modes.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking robustness will be evaluated via bootstrap analysis with 1,000 resamples of the clinical test set. The stability of the outcome will be quantified using the Kendall rank correlation coefficient (τ) and its 95% confidence interval (CI), ensuring that the final leaderboard is statistically reliable and resistant to test-set bias.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

A Paired t-test (or Wilcoxon signed-rank test if data is not normally distributed) will be used to compare the top-performing methods. Significance level is set at $p < 0.05$.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing data is handled via worst-case penalization. Specifically, IoU, LDSC, and RQ are set to 0, while ASSD and HD95 are assigned the radius and diameter of the fragment's minimum enclosing sphere, respectively.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python (SciPy, NumPy, Matplotlib, etc.)

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

A dockerized interactive baseline model will be provided for benchmarking. Subsequent analyses will document inter-algorithm variability to provide insights into the comparative effectiveness of interactive segmentation methods. Furthermore, we will stratify performance analysis by "Fracture Complexity" (according to AO/OTA classification) to identify potential biases and ensure clinical generalizability.

Reference:

- [1] Ge, Yufeng, et al. "Robot-assisted autonomous reduction of a displaced pelvic fracture: a case report and brief literature review." *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 11.6 (2022): 1598.
- [2] Marinov, Zdravko and Jäger, Paul F., et al. "Deep interactive segmentation of medical images: A systematic review and taxonomy." *IEEE TPAMI* (2024).
- [3] Sang, Yudi, et al. "Benchmark of Segmentation Techniques for Pelvic Fracture in CT and X-ray: Summary of the PENGWIN 2024 Challenge." *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.02382* (2025).
- [4] Liu, Wentao, et al. "Transforming the interactive segmentation for medical imaging." *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2022.
- [5] Mikhailov, Ivan, et al. "A deep learning-based interactive medical image segmentation framework." *International Workshop on Applications of Medical AI*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2022.
- [6] Luo, Xiangde, et al. "MIDeepSeg: Minimally interactive segmentation of unseen objects from medical images using deep learning." *Medical image analysis* 72 (2021): 102102.
- [7] Sakinis, Tomas, et al. "Interactive segmentation of medical images through fully convolutional neural networks." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1903.08205* (2019).

TASK 3: PENGWIN-Reduction: Peripelvic Fracture Reduction Planning

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Peripelvic injuries are among the most severe forms of orthopedic trauma, with disability rates of 50–60% and mortality exceeding 13% [1,2]. Successful surgical treatment relies heavily on the accurate restoration of pelvic ring anatomy, known as fracture reduction. Conventionally, preoperative planning involves manually manipulating virtual bone fragments in 3D software [3,4], which is time-consuming, subjective, and requires substantial clinical expertise [5].

While segmentation identifies where the fragments are, accurately restoring multiple spatially separated fragments remains the central challenge of reduction planning. In the absence of patient-specific pre-injury templates and under substantial anatomical variability, algorithms must handle an unknown number of fragments with arbitrary positions and orientations, without a global reference. Consequently, fracture reduction becomes a high-dimensional, non-convex geometric matching and joint optimization problem, representing a major computational bottleneck in intelligent surgical planning pipelines.

Task 3 of the PENGWIN 2026 challenge targets this restoration problem. Participants are provided with segmented and spatially separated pelvic fracture fragments derived from the ground truth annotations of Task 1. The dataset includes 500 clinically representative cases covering complex pelvic ring fractures, joint dislocations, acetabular fractures, and proximal femoral fractures. To mitigate the scarcity of large-scale clinical data for training data-driven reduction models, the challenge further incorporates 16,000 simulated fracture cases generated from 400 healthy pelvic CT scans sourced from the CTPelvic1K dataset [6]. Multiple state-of-the-art fracture simulation methods-including Voronoi [7], BreakingGood [8], BDRD [9], and DFGM [10]-are used to ensure diverse and realistic fracture patterns. These simulated data have been shown to improve the learning of fracture-specific geometric priors and generalization to clinical scenarios, while providing mathematically precise ground-truth reductions based on pre-injury anatomy [9,10].

By establishing a unified benchmark for peripelvic fracture reduction planning, this task aims to advance automated reduction planning algorithms and support the development of robot-assisted surgery and intelligent surgical navigation systems, ultimately improving surgical efficiency and patient outcomes.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Peripelvic fractures, Reduction planning, Pose estimation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Sutuke Yibulayimu, Beihang University

Yanzhen Liu, Beihang University

Yudi Sang, Rossum Robot

Yu Wang, Beihang University

Gang Zhu, Rossum Robot

Chunpeng Zhao, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital

Yufeng Ge, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital

Xinbao Wu, Beijing Jishuitan Hospital

Ronald Man Yeung Wong, CUHK Medical Centre

Elvis Chun Sing Chui, CUHK Medical Centre

Mehran Armand, Johns Hopkins University

Dan Ruan, University of California, Los Angeles

S. Kevin Zhou, University of Science and Technology of China

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Sutuke Yibulayimu

Beihang University

sutuk@buaa.edu.cn

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Clinicians from Beijing Jishuitan Hospital and CUHK Medical Centre are integral to the team. Their roles include: (1) Guiding the data acquisition protocol to ensure clinical relevance; (2) Validating the "fracture diversity" of the simulated data to ensure it reflects real-world trauma patterns; (3) Providing expert annotations (ground truth) for the clinical cases.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

A challenge website is planned to be launched upon acceptance of the challenge proposal.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic. No user interaction is allowed at any step

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may supplement the training dataset with additional data from public datasets or their own institutions. Furthermore, participants are welcomed to develop their own simulation pipelines using open-source non-fracture CT datasets to further boost model generalizability. However, if they choose to do so, they must specify and discuss the potential differences in results compared to using only the PENGWIN 2026 dataset. Any external data used must be publicly available.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 teams will receive cash awards (\$1000, \$500, and \$200, funded by Rossum Robot) and certificates. They will be invited to co-author the challenge summary paper.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be shown publicly on the challenge leaderboard, which will be updated daily during the open validation round and announced on the final round phases of the closed test round of the task.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The challenge organizers will publish at least one challenge journal paper and potentially more. Up to two team members in each of the top-performing teams qualify as authors for joint publication. Participants are allowed to publish their results separately after the challenge. The publication embargo period will be 12 months after the announcement of the challenge results.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission on Grand Challenge.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants can have multiple submissions on the validation data during the validation phase. For the testing phase, only the last run of the submitted Docker container is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge websites open: 04/01/2026

Training data release: 04/05/2026

Validation data release and results submission: 05/15/2026

Final Submission deadline: 07/31/2026

Result release: 08/31/2026

Presentation at conference: 10/2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

(1) **Clinical Dataset:** The retrospective data collection, share, and usage strictly conformed to ethical standards and was approved by the ethical committee of Beijing Jishuitan Hospital (Approval number 202009-04).

(2) **Simulated Data:** Derived from the publicly available and de-identified CTPelvic1K dataset [6], used in strict compliance with its original institutional ethical standards and open-access terms.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The metric calculation code will be released along with the validation data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The top 3 performing methods are required to share their code on a public repository. Other teams are also encouraged to share their code. Links to the available source code will be referenced on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is sponsored by Rossum Robot. Only the organizers (Rossum Robot, IMR Lab of Beihang University, BIGSS Lab and ARCADE Lab of Johns Hopkins University and cv:hci Lab of Karlsruhe Institute of Technology) will have access to the test case labels during the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Surgery, Intervention planning, CAD, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Reconstruction, Restoration, Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients with peripelvic fractures requiring reduction surgery.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

A dual-source cohort consisting of:

(1) Clinical sub-cohort: The subject of peripelvic trauma who planned to undergo reduction surgery after pre-operative CT scanning.

(2) Simulated sub-cohort: The subject of intact peripelvic anatomy whose CT scans were used as the basis for fracture simulation.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed tomography (CT) processed into 3D Surface Meshes

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

(1) Fragment Data: The input for each case consists of multiple spatially separated 3D fragments, each representing a bone fragment. To accommodate varying computational resources, we will release the fracture reduction dataset in two formats: the "Original Mesh Version" (.stl), allowing participants to implement custom preprocessing pipelines, and a "Pre-processed Point Cloud Version" (.npz), specifically provided to assist participants by eliminating the need for complex preprocessing while offering a significantly smaller file size. This allows teams to utilize ready-to-use data and focus directly on model development.

(2) Reduction Poses: 6-DoF transformation matrices for each fragment (provided for the training set as ground truth) to define the target anatomic alignment.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No further patient information will be provided.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Peripelvic bone fragments derived from CT scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The target of the algorithm is the displaced bone fragments of the fractured peripelvic region. The goal is to calculate the 6-DoF transformations required for precise anatomic restoration.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision, Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT scans were acquired using a diverse array of devices from multiple manufacturers, including TOSHIBA (Aquilion PRIME, Aquilion ONE), UNITED IMAGING (uCT 550), PHILIPS (Brilliance 64), SIEMENS (Sensation 64, SOMATOM Force), and GE (Optima CT660).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

(1) Clinical Data: Clinically-used routine CT protocols have been used in each CT scanner. During the acquisition process, all patients were positioned in supine pose. The average voxel spacing is $0.81 \times 0.81 \times 0.93 \text{ mm}^3$. The typical image dimensions average at $483 \times 385 \times 320$.

(2) Simulated Data: CT scanning of healthy subjects covering the peripelvic region (average resolution: $0.75 \times 0.75 \times 0.81 \text{ mm}^3$; average size: $512 \times 512 \times 323$), utilized for fracture simulation via Voronoi, BreakingGood, DFGM, and BDRD algorithms [7-10].

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

(1) Clinical Data: The CT data for this challenge were acquired from a multi-center consortium comprising seven clinical institutions to ensure data diversity and robustness. These centers include Beijing Jishuitan Hospital, Foshan Hospital of Traditional Chinese Medicine, The First Hospital of Jilin University, The Second Hospital of Jilin University, Nanfang Hospital (Southern Medical University), Tongji Hospital, and CUHK Medical Centre.

(2) Simulated Data: The open-source CTPelvic1K dataset (COLONOG subset) [6].

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

CT acquisition was performed by professional radiologists.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to a single peripelvic fracture instance (either clinical or simulated) comprising a set of surface meshes for all spatially separated bone fragments, with 6-DoF restoration poses provided for each bone fragment as the reference standard.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

- (1) Clinical cases: 500 cases are split into 350 for training, 50 for validation, and 100 for testing.
- (2) Simulation cases: 400 healthy subjects are split into 280 for training, 40 for validation, and 80 for testing. With 40 fracture instances generated per subject, this results in 11,200 training, 1,600 validation, and 3,200 testing cases.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

- (1) Clinical Diversity and Efficiency: The 100 clinical test cases cover diverse fracture patterns and scanner types. This sample size ensures statistically robust results while maintaining manageable computational costs on the assessment platform.
- (2) Hybrid Data Strategy: Large-scale simulated data serves as the training backbone due to its mathematically exact ground truth. A clinical subset is provided to bridge the sim-to-real domain gap through fine-tuning, joint training, or domain adaptation.
- (3) Benchmark Hierarchy: The Clinical Test Set is the primary target for final ranking to reflect real-world surgical scenarios. The Simulated Test Set is utilized to assess the theoretical geometric upper bound of the algorithms.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

To ensure a balanced and representative evaluation, we employed stratified random sampling based on peripelvic injury patterns. This ensures that the training, validation, and test sets share the same distribution of fracture types.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

- (1) **Clinical Novelty:** The clinical dataset comprises 500 cases: 150 are carried over from PENGWIN 2024, while 350 cases are brand new, unseen, and previously unpublished. These new cases have been incorporated into the dataset for this challenge.
- (2) **Pioneering Annotations:** All reduction planning labels (6-DoF matrices) are entirely new. This challenge provides the first-ever open-source reference standard for peripelvic fracture reduction planning.
- (3) **Original Simulation:** This challenge introduces the first large-scale, open-source simulated dataset dedicated to fracture restoration. Previously, no such comprehensive public training data with diverse fracture patterns and precise ground-truth poses existed in the research community.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The reference standard (6-DoF transformation matrices) is determined by three experienced annotators and two senior experts through a multi-stage process:

- (1) **Mesh Generation:** High-quality surface meshes are extracted from the refined anatomical segmentations of each bone fragment.
- (2) **Virtual Interactive Restoration (Clinical):** For clinical cases, annotators manually realign the fragmented meshes into their anatomically correct positions using 3D virtual tools. The alignment is guided by fracture surface congruency, cortical continuity, and global anatomical plausibility.
- (3) **Mathematical Extraction (Simulated):** For simulated cases, the transformation matrices are mathematically derived by comparing the generated fragments with the original, intact healthy bone configuration, providing a precise gold standard.
- (4) **Expert Validation:** As a final checkpoint, two senior experts rigorously review all restored configurations. Any case that does not meet clinical plausibility or anatomical precision is either refined or excluded.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotators are professional orthopedic surgeons using our proprietary 3D restoration platform. The annotators are asked to:

- (1) Maximize fracture surface congruency by matching unique fracture line patterns through precise interactive 3D manipulation.
- (2) Ensure seamless cortical continuity across all fragment interfaces to minimize step-off deformities and ensure a clinically anatomical fit.
- (3) Verify global anatomical plausibility by utilizing overall pelvic ring symmetry and the contralateral side as reference templates.
- (4) Flag any case with ambiguous anatomical landmarks for joint review by the senior expert panel to ensure clinical validity and reach a final consensus.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The dataset is processed by three experienced annotators and two senior experts. All of them has more than five year experience on pelvis-related study or surgery.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The pre-processing pipeline standardizes raw clinical and simulated data into a unified 3D mesh format for the reduction planning task:

(1) Clinical Data: Raw CT segmentations are first converted into high-resolution surface meshes using the Marching Cubes algorithm. These meshes undergo decimation to achieve a uniform vertex density, ensuring a balance between geometric fidelity and computational efficiency across all clinical instances. For each clinical case, the reference standard is established by extracting the 6-DoF transformation matrices required to restore fragments from their randomized initial poses back to the expert-validated anatomic alignment.

(2) Simulated Data: Large-scale simulated fracture instances are generated from healthy templates using four distinct pipelines to capture diverse clinical morphologies, including Voronoi-based [7] decomposition for comminuted patterns, BreakingGood [8] for physics-informed structural failure, Deformable Fracture Generation Model (DFGM) [10] for complex surface topologies, and Bone density-weighted Random Distance map (BDRD) [9] for density-guided fractures.

(3) Initial Pose Generation: Regarding the randomization of fracture poses, we adopt a runtime domain randomization strategy rather than static physical simulation. We will provide the specific dataloader used to dynamically generate initial poses within clinically observed ranges of rotation and translation during training. Unlike static simulation, which limits diversity, this approach exposes models to a vast continuous space of pose configurations, significantly enhancing robustness across the full clinical scope.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The primary source of annotation error stems from subjective judgment during virtual restoration, particularly in approximately 10% of cases involving severe comminution or ambiguous half-cracked and connected patterns. In these scenarios, the lack of distinct cortical landmarks or bone attrition increases inter-observer variability when defining the optimal anatomical fit.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

(1) Segmentation and Meshing Artifacts: Potential errors propagated from the initial segmentation or mesh decimation can result in smoothed fracture edges.

(2) Sim-to-Real Domain Gap: While simulated data provides a mathematically exact reference standard, minor discrepancies in surface texture and fracture surface complexity compared to real-world cases may affect the generalizability of algorithms.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- (1) Rotation Error (Rot) - degrees;
- (2) Translation Error (Trans) - mm;
- (3) Target Registration Error (TRE) - mm;
- (4) Chamfer Distance (CD) - mm;
- (5) Part Accuracy (PA) - %.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The selected metrics provide a multi-dimensional evaluation of fracture reduction planning by balancing mathematical rigor with clinical relevance. As the primary objective is the estimation of a 6-DoF restoration matrix, Rotation (Rot) and Translation (Trans) errors are fundamental, independently assessing the algorithm's geometric reasoning through the geodesic distance in $SO(3)$ and Euclidean distance between predicted and reference vectors. To synthesize these pose components into a physically meaningful measure of surgical displacement, the Target Reduction Error (TRE) calculates the root-mean-square error (RMSE) of all fragment vertex coordinates, directly quantifying the anatomical misalignment in millimeters. In contrast to coordinate-specific TRE, the Chamfer Distance (CD) evaluates the symmetric average distance between point sets to prioritize global shape similarity and surface congruency. This metric is particularly critical for addressing geometric ambiguity in fragments that lack distinct anatomical landmarks or exhibit rotational symmetry/isotropy, where multiple transformation configurations may yield a physically equivalent "lock-and-key" fit despite variations in the underlying matrix. Finally, Part Accuracy (PA) serves as a high-level "success rate" by measuring the percentage of fragments successfully restored within predefined clinical tolerances. This provides an intuitive benchmark for orthopedic surgeons to evaluate the algorithm's overall reliability.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

We adopt a rank-then-aggregate method focused on clinical applicability, ensuring that the performance on multi-fragment cases is accurately captured:

- (1) Metric Aggregation per Case: For each clinical case consisting of N bone fragments, the 5 metrics (Rot, Trans, TRE, CD) are first calculated for each fragment independently. The Case-level Score is determined by averaging the results across all fragments within that specific case. Part Accuracy (PA) for a case is defined as the ratio of successfully restored fragments to the total number of fragments.
- (2) Ranking Scope: The Official Leaderboard Rank is determined solely by performance on the Clinical Test Set.

Simulated Test Set results are reported for theoretical analysis (e.g., geometric upper-bound evaluation) but do not contribute to the final ranking.

(3) Ranking Logic: For the Clinical Test Set, participating teams are ranked for each of the 5 metrics (Rot, Trans, TRE, CD, PA) separately. The Final Rank is determined by averaging these 5 individual ranks.

(4) Tie-Breaking: In the event of a tie in the Final Rank, the team with the lower mean Target Reduction Error (TRE) on the Clinical Test Set will be ranked higher.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result for a specific case (missing output), the transformation matrix will be assumed to be the Identity Matrix (i.e., assuming no reduction movement). The metrics (Rot, Trans, TRE, CD, PA) will be calculated based on this initial displaced state. This approach naturally penalizes the failure with high error values corresponding to the initial fracture displacement, allowing for a continuous metric evaluation without assigning arbitrary infinite values.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

(1) The "Rank-then-Aggregate" scheme ensures a robust and clinically relevant assessment. Ranking teams across five distinct metrics (Rot, Trans, TRE, CD, and PA) and averaging these ranks prevents a single outlier from disproportionately skewing the leaderboard.

(2) Basing the Official Leaderboard Rank solely on the Clinical Test Set ensures results reflect true utility in real-world surgical scenarios involving biological variability and imaging artifacts.

(3) Averaging metrics across all fragments within a case accurately represents the complexity of comminuted fractures, where every fragment's alignment is critical for peripelvic stability.

(4) Target Reduction Error (TRE) serves as the tie-breaker as it provides a comprehensive measurement of pose accuracy, integrating both rotational and translational errors into a single physical displacement value.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will report the Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and 95% Confidence Intervals (CI) for all metrics.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Precision of the performance estimates for each algorithm will be assessed using 95% confidence intervals (CI) calculated via percentile bootstrap (1,000 resamples). This will be applied to all primary metrics, including Rot, Trans, TRE, CD, and PA, to quantify the statistical reliability of each team's reported performance across the clinical test set.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Box plots will be used to visualize the distribution of metrics across test cases. We will report the Standard Deviation (SD) and identify outliers (cases beyond 1.5x IQR) to analyze failure modes.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking robustness will be evaluated via bootstrap analysis with 1,000 resamples of the clinical test set. The stability of the outcome will be quantified using the Kendall rank correlation coefficient (τ) and its 95% confidence interval (CI), ensuring that the final leaderboard is statistically reliable and resistant to test-set bias.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

A Paired t-test (or Wilcoxon signed-rank test if data is not normally distributed) will be used to compare the top-performing methods. Significance level is set at $p < 0.05$.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Consistent with the scoring policy, cases with missing outputs are assigned the Identity Matrix (initial displaced pose). These cases are included in the statistical analysis with their resulting high error values, ensuring they impact the mean/median performance metrics appropriately.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python (SciPy, NumPy, Matplotlib, etc.)

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will provide a validated baseline model [10] capable of handling all fracture types, complete with pre-trained weights derived from our dataset. Additionally, a tutorial demonstrating the full reduction pipeline will be included. Furthermore, we will stratify performance analysis by "Fracture Complexity" (according to AO/OTA classification) and "Simulation Gaps" to identify potential biases and ensure clinical generalizability.

Reference:

- [1] Halawi, M.J., 2016. Pelvic ring injuries: Surgical management and long-term outcomes. *J. Clin. Orthop. Trauma* 7 (1), 1–6.
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- [4] A. S. Chowdhury, S. M. Bhandarkar, R. W. Robinson, and C. Y. Jack, "Virtual multi-fracture craniofacial reconstruction using computer vision and graph matching," *Computerized Medical Imaging and Graphics*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 333–342, 2009.
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- [6] P. Liu, H. Han, Y. Du, H. Zhu, Y. Li, F. Gu, H. Xiao, J. Li, C. Zhao, L. Xiao et al., "Deep learning to segment pelvic

bones: large-scale ct datasets and baseline models," International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery, vol. 16, pp. 749–756, 2021.

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[8] Sellán S, Luong J, Mattos Da Silva L, et al. Breaking good: Fracture modes for realtime destruction[J]. ACM Transactions on Graphics, 2023, 42(1): 1-12.

[9] B. Zeng, H. Wang, X. Tao, H. Shi, L. Joskowitz, and X. Chen, "A bidirectional framework for fracture simulation and deformation-based restoration prediction in pelvic fracture surgical planning," Medical Image Analysis, vol. 97, p. 103267, 2024.

[10] S. Yibulayimu et al., "FracFormer: Fracture Reduction Planning With Transformer-Based Shape Restoration and Fracture Data Simulation," in IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, vol. 44, no. 8, pp. 3270-3283, Aug. 2025.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

The organizing team has a distinguished background, with key members being leaders in their respective fields. Prof. Mehran Armand and Prof. Yu Wang are renowned for their contributions to medical robotics research. Prof. Mathias Unberath, Prof. Dan Ruan, and Prof. S. Kevin Zhou bring a wealth of expertise in the realms of deep learning and medical imaging. Prof. Rainer Stiefelhagen and Zdravko Marinov bring expertise from the fields of computer vision and interactive segmentation of medical images. In the clinical domain, Dr. Xinbao Wu and Dr. Chunpeng Zhao are joined by Prof. Ronald Man Yeung Wong and Prof. Elvis Chun Sing Chui from the CUHK Medical Centre, serving as leading experts in Orthopaedics and Traumatology. Both Beijing Jishuitan Hospital and the CUHK Medical Centre are recognized as leading institutions in orthopedics and traumatology. This diverse expertise ensures a comprehensive and informed approach to the challenge.